

COLOUR REMOVAL FROM DYE EFFLUENT USING ACTIVATED CARBON FROM TAMARIND SHELL

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ABSTRACT

In 21st century, water pollution due to textile dye industry has turned into a severe problem around the world including India. The dye industry in India is made up of about 85 large organized units and 4,000 small scale units, they produce around 1,60,000tonnes of dyestuff per month. These direct discharges of dye wastewater effluent into waterbodies like lakes, rivers and other water pollution will affect plants and animals. The aim of our research is to prepare activated carbon from tamarind shell with surface modification by chemically activating method in optimum conditions with distilled water. Availability, cheapness and adsorption capacity are the key factors for choosing tamarind shell as a particular source for activated carbon. The study undergoes the effects of contact time, powdered activated carbon dosage, and effect of rpm in adsorption between chemically activated carbon and dye waste water. The amount of activated carbon yield from the tamarind shell is 59.5% and it is also cheaply available waste material. The maximum removal efficiency of 99.7% was achieved at 60 rpm with optimum contact time 90 minutes and optimum dosage of 5g powdered activated carbon.

1. Introduction

The primary necessity for human survival on earth is water. Declining water quality as a result of inadequate wastewater treatment is a challenge that many nations worldwide are dealing with. Our biological variety is affected both directly and indirectly by this crisis, disrupting the entire global ecosystem. Water contamination brought on by the textile dye industry has become a serious issue in the twenty-first century, and this includes India. One of the concerns with the sustainability of water resources is present in India. A dye is an improperly powdered solid that is combined with another substance or dissolved in a

liquid, such as paint or ink. Finely powdered solid pigments are disseminated in a liquid^[1]. Industries that employ dyes include those that produce paper and pulp, dye clothing and textiles, treat leather, print on food goods, etc. Their waste products are heavily colored^[2]. Due to its high specific surface area and wide micro porosity, activated carbon is employed extensively nowadays. The activated carbon purports to be black in colour and has a significant amount of micropores. Low cost wastewater treatment of streams with low concentrations is another application for activated carbon adsorption. For dangerous contaminants, activated carbon has a very high removal efficiency^[22]. Consequently, several researchers have looked at the removal of colour pollutants from water using activated carbon made from natural and affordable agricultural wastes such as banana peels, orange peels, lemon peels, peanut shells, bamboo shoots, and coconut shells^[13]. Many nanomaterials have been created and used as adsorbents to remove contaminants from liquid phases. Due to their low expenses and remarkable decontamination effectiveness, iron and aluminum-based nanoscale adsorbent materials were among the first inorganic nanomaterials to be studied^[3]. The desired features of the adsorbent material, such as its non-toxicity, simplicity in preparation, high capacity, and capacity to absorb impurities, as well as its ability to be recycled, determine an adsorbent's effectiveness^[17]. The pH, size of adsorbents, dye concentration, temperature, etc. all affect how well dye adsorbs^[10]. The use of bio adsorbent has the potential to recover metal after adsorption phenomenon, as well as remove pollutants with high efficiency, reduce biological sludge, and be easily reproduced. The interactions of hydroxyl groups with the dye molecules have been suggested as the cause of the enormous capacity for adsorption of magnetized adsorbents for dyes^[7]. Activated clay, activated carbon, activated slag, chitosan beads, cellulosic resin, polymer resin, chemically modified rice husk, cross-linked starch, palm kernel fibre, red mud, bottom ash, ion exchangers, and granulated ferric hydroxide are just a few of the adsorbent materials used to absorb the dye molecules and then remove the colour from water^[5]. These adsorbents come in a variety of prices and performance levels. However due to its outstanding ability to adsorb dye impurities, activated carbon is one of the most often utilised adsorbents for colour removal^[23]. By transferring one or more components (the adsorbate) to the interior surface of a porous solid (the adsorbent), where they are retained by intermolecular interactions, adsorption is the separation of components in certain fluid

mixes^[8].

2. Materials and methods

Methylene blue was removed from dye effluent using an adsorption study. Dark green powdered methylene blue dye dissolves in water to form a blue solution. At room temperature, methylene blue appears as an odorless solid. Strong adsorption characteristics are present in solids with a maximum absorption wavelength of 668 nm. With the chemical formula $C_{16}H_{18}ClN_3S$, methylene blue, often known as Basic Blue 9, is defined as 3,7-bis (Dimethyl amino) phenazathionium chloride tetramethylthionine chloride. A cationic dye with a molecular weight of 319.85 g/mole is methylene blue.

The sample of dye effluent is taken from one small-scale dye factory in Arupukottai. Methylene blue has been identified as the dye sample. Tamarind shells are gathered in order to prepare activated carbon for use as an adsorbent.

2.1 Preparation of Activated Carbon

Tamarind Shells were collected and then cut into small pieces, followed by washing with tap water for removal of dust particles adhere to it. Then it was dried in the sunlight for 3 days. Dried tamarind shells were kept inside the furnace at 150°C for 24 hours for removal of moisture and other volatile impurities. After that it was crushed and sieved to 300-700 μm size range.

Chemical Activation of the powdered material was done with $ZnCl_2$ to make the Impregnation Ratio (Activating agent/powdered tamarind shell) 100% (500 gm of dried tamarind shell was well mixed with 3000 ml of concentrated solution of $ZnCl_2$ that contains 500 gm of $ZnCl_2$). The slurry form of powder tamarind shell was properly mixed and kept for 24 hours for proper soaking of $ZnCl_2$ on its surface. The slurry was kept inside the oven at 100°C for 24 hours.

In this work $ZnCl_2$ acts as dehydration reagent lowers the carbonization temperature during chemical activation. The resulting chemical impregnated samples were kept inside the muffle furnace for 1 hr at 650°C. Then it was cooled. The washing process of dry material was initially carried with 0.5 N HCl for 2-3 times which was then carried on with

warm distilled water to remove different residual organic and mineral matter. Which was then finally washed with cold water until the solution becomes neutral. Finally, the sample was dried for 24 hours at 100°C inside an oven and packed in an air tight container.

Physical activation or chemical activation can be used to create activated carbon. The tamarind shell is used to make activated carbon, which is then chemically activated. As a chemical activation reagent, ZnCl_2 and HCL are utilized. The characteristics of activated carbon are listed in IS 877:1989, which details the processes for sampling and testing for both powdered and granular activated carbons. The outcomes are compared to IS 8366:1989, which specifies the types and parameters for powdered and granular activated carbons.

To determine the physical characteristics of the activated carbon, such as surface topography, texture, particle size, and porosity, a scanning electron microscopic test is carried out. The SEM test was conducted under ideal conditions, with a working distance of 9,000 μm and a magnification of 1,000.

Figure 2.2 SEM images of activated carbon before chemical activation

The SEM picture of tamarind shell was derived activated carbon before chemical activation. The image in this case shows that the particles have an irregular shape, an average particle size of 60 μm , and a greyish appearance. After chemical activation, the activated carbon made from tamarind shell appears light grey in colour and has irregularly shaped particles with an average particle size of 10 μm , according to the SEM image.

Significant variations between the texture and pore size of activated carbon before and after chemical activation were seen in the SEM pictures. Volatiles are eliminated as a result of chemical activation and carbonization, and pores are effectively developed.

Figure 2.3 SEM images of activated carbon after chemical activation

3. Results and Discussion

Preliminary tests such as pH, Total, dissolved, suspended solids, BOD, COD were conducted for collected dye wastewater.

Table 3.1 Initial characteristics of dye effluent

Physical and chemical characteristics	Before adsorption
pH	8.5
Suspended solids	620 mg/l
Amount of Total solids	560 mg/L
Amount of Dissolved solids	740 mg/L
COD of taken sample	61.008mg/L
Bod 5 (in mg/l)	52.5mg/L

In order to prepare standard calibration curve prior dye adsorption test, different concentration of methylene blue solution was prepared and analyzed using UV-Vis Spectrophotometer. The performance of functionalized activated carbon was analyzed by manipulating temperature, contact time between adsorbent and adsorbate and granular activated carbon dosage for dye adsorption test.

The dosage of activated carbon is an important factor because the amount of adsorption depends more on it. By increasing the dosage from 0.1 gram to 0.5 gram we can find the optimum dosage in which more adsorption takes place.

Figure 3.1 Colour detection by using Activated carbon

Table 3.2 % of color removal by adsorption at 150 rpm

Time(min)	30 min	60min	90min	120min	150min
Dosage(gm)					
0.1	48.53	47.35	49.71	26.76	24.7
0.2	44.12	50	52.35	38.53	20.8
0.3	63.23	58.53	67.35	47.06	15.7
0.4	84.12	83.53	80.88	82.65	6.2
0.5	98.67	92.35	88.23	93.23	3

Figure 3.2 % of color removal at 120 rpm**Figure 3.4 % of color removal at 60 rpm**

3.1 Effect of Contact Time

Based on the results obtained from the above graph plotted in Figure 3.4 and Figure 3.5, it can be observed that for 30 minutes the colour adsorption is less, for the time of 60 minutes the adsorption is low, but for the time of 90 min the adsorption is more but for 120 min the adsorption is lesser. This is because for more than 90 minutes time desorption takes place. So, we take the 60 minutes as the optimum time for the adsorption.

3.2 Effect of r.p.m.

As the adsorption process depends more on the rpm in which it rotates. For the 30 rpm the adsorption is low, for 60 rpm the adsorption is more, for 90 rpm the adsorption is low, this means that the desorption takes place. So, in 60 rpm the maximum adsorption takes place.

3.3 Effect of Powdered Activated Carbon Dosage

The dosage of activated carbon is an important factor because the amount of adsorption depends more on it. By increasing the dosage from 0.1 gram to 0.5 gram we can find the optimum dosage in which more adsorption takes place. The maximum adsorption takes place at the dosage of 0.5 gram per 200ml of sample. By adding the dosage more than the activated carbon becomes waste.

CONCLUSION

The main objective of this project was to evaluate the efficiency of powdered activated carbon arrived from tamarind shell for colour removal of methylene blue dye from textile effluent and to understand the colour removal process and adsorption phenomena. The Powdered Activated Carbon from tamarind shell has been found to be efficient for the removal of colour of dye industry wastewater as evident from batch experiments using a wide range of initial colour concentrations. A maximum of 99.7% removal of colour was obtained from our experiments. Availability, cheapness and adsorption capacity are the key factors for choosing tamarind shell as a particular source for activated carbon. The amount of activated carbon yield from the tamarind shell is 59.5% and it is also cheaply available waste material. The maximum removal efficiency of 99.7% was achieved at 60 rpm with optimum contact time 90 minutes and optimum dosage of 5g powdered activated carbon.

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